

ADDRESSING FLOODING RISK IN THE HUTT VALLEY FLOODPLAIN

~ *What are our options?*

Abstract

Climate change will put New Zealand's urban areas at greater risk of flooding. We examine the Hutt River Flood Plain Management Plan and other available literature to identify policy options for addressing flood risk in the region. We find that the Plan's existing response to risk – a focus on structural controls is necessary but not sufficient to address flooding risks. We examine root causes for this gap. We propose a more comprehensive approach, recommending policy options that include, funding and prioritisation for non-structural methods, including, but not limited to land-use policies, based on sound, explicit analysis and comprehensive engagement with stakeholders of the Hutt River Flood Plain.

Introduction

Climate change will result in increased precipitation, which will put urban areas at greater risk of flooding. This is likely to be the case for New Zealand cities: in particular, the Hutt City of New Zealand's North Island.

The primary objective of this paper is to identify policy options for improved long-run ecological value in the context of increased flooding risk in urban environments, utilising the specific example of the Hutt Valley.

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The policy options aim to protect the region from recurrent floods and other anticipated harms from climate change - improving the local resilience of the population and its infrastructure.

We have considered the need for continued, multi-factor productivity growth in the region - attracting, for instance, investors firms, house holders and high-value trading of goods and services – whilst using a combination of the market mechanisms and government mandate to protect vulnerable families exposed to risk.

We have attempted to highlight limitations in performing further analysis. Where possible, we have used evidence of status quo policies, publically available data and research.

Flooding in the Lower Hutt Region – What we know so far

The Lower Hutt region has been historically prone to severe flooding. 20 flood events are recorded between 1840-1890. The flood event in 1898 was the largest and record at 2000 cumecs – which covered the entire Valley floor. [5]

The Region has since undergone simultaneous development of flood protection, urbanisation and decline of local ecological integrity.

According to Ministry for the Environment reports regional climate change projections based on the IPCC's

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fourth assessment report (2007) and NIWA's regional climate model show that the Wellington region (1990 to 2040) has a change in temperature range of 0.3 to 2.2°C with an average increase of 0.9 °C. This could cause a change in seasonal and annual precipitation with Parapaumu (located on Wellingtons west coast) ranging between -3 and +10% [5][7]

The Hutt City's response to flooding has been risk-based. A significant emphasis has been placed on structural controls (building stopbanks, protecting the sides of the river with rock and plantings of willows and natives) and includes some 'softer measures to address this risk.

However, flood risk exposure to residents remain significant: Estimates of impact from 2000 cumecs suggest approximately 106,000 residents and up to \$6 billion of property is at risk.[5]

According to a study sponsored by the Victoria University's New Zealand Climate Change Research Institute study: "The HRFPMMP does not give much regard to the potential for large future changes in flood frequencies. Based on the results presented in this study, floods may have already become more frequent in 30 years time when the plan is due to be completed." [7]

Nearly 130,000 people live in the Valley, mostly on its floodplain.

Also, structural controls in place do not cover all residential areas. Minor streams that can flood cause significant disruption to the region overall: For instance, the latest flood event in November 12, 2016 of the Waiwhetu stream flood event affected several households, closed schools, disrupted NCEA exams and caused the failure of the sewage system. There were similar events in 1976 and 2004.

Risk models currently do not account for rising sea levels, which is likely to also increase the water tables in low-lying areas, such as Petone.

The compounding effects of flood risk, sea level rise and other risks such as liquefaction risks due to earthquakes and intense urbanisation calls for a fresh look at key options for mitigation.

Greater Wellington Region's Response to this risk

The Hutt River Floodplain Management Plan (HRFPMP) provides the basis for the management of flood risk – for structural and non structural controls.

These structural controls are:

1. Stopbanks
2. Bank Edge Protection
3. House Raising
4. Bridge Replacement

Importantly, the risks that are "left over" (residual risks) are provided for by non-structural measures, which, within the Plan are:

1. land-use management
2. emergency management preparedness.

Cost effectiveness of status-quo measures

The Plan proposes to spend an estimated \$78 million on physical works over the next 40 years to achieve the 2300 cumec risk-based design standard.

We look at cost effectiveness of this expenditure from the focus of the primary purpose of this paper – to improve long term ecological value. We use the same indicators as in the HRFPMMP:

Measure	Is it cost effective?
Degree of ecological improvement provided by reduced erosion*	Inconclusive. There are no authoritative data supporting the progress of this indicator.
Presence of ecological and conservation sites in the river corridor and on the floodplain	Not Cost Effective. There is less than 1% planned increase in ecological or conservation sites in relation to the overall flood plain area
increases in the number of indigenous species in the Hutt River environment	Not cost effective. There are no evidence of increase in indigenous (or other wildlife species) to a scale that will evidentially meet control objectives.

Measure	Is it cost effective?
Recreation Flood-prone area affected as an indicator of the damage extent	Not Cost Effective. Recreation areas have been affected by flooding. However, further analysis is needed to quantify how much area is affected.
Recreation Flood-prone area affected as an indicator of the damage extent Presence of parks and reserves	Not Cost effective. There has been no increase in parks and reserves – with no plan to do so.

We find that the status quo, structural approach is *necessary but not sufficient* to address flood risk, protect the long-run ecological value of the Hutt Region.

What is proposed

The New Zealand Climate Change Research Institute report found that there is “a need for a more comprehensive approach across New Zealand to changes in flood risk associated with climate change.”[7]

We propose a substantive review of the controls and methodology used to address flood risk in the Hutt Valley. We support our view based on current international and local research and have studied progressive land-use strategies in other governments – most notably, the Scottish Government. [10]

Prioritise and fund non-structural methods, including, but not limited to land-use policies based on explicit economic analysis.

Whilst the HRFPM states that “non-structural methods are particularly cost effective”, there is no analysis provided to support this. We propose that the ratio of expenditure between structural measures and non-structural measures should be defined in planning and budget documentation in order to inform economic analysis.

“For existing development in flood-prone areas, effort is put into raising flood awareness and preparedness, which should reduce flood damage, and the trauma and stress associated with flooding. “ Embracing Modern Ways, HRFPM.

Toward this aim, we found that 5% of Capital Expend-

iture works on structural controls is allocated to structural environmental controls: planting of natives and willows. Whilst this helps analysis, substantive more financial data needs to be made public in order to identify opportunities for optimisation.

Policy Objective: Optimise the restoration of the Hutt Valley Floodplain back to its original ecological state using economic, social incentives and technological controls.

We have identified options that support our proposed policy objective of restoring the floodplain to its original state – as far as economically viable.

A. “Land Use for Nature” - Make Ecological Integrity a priority.

This objective is about prioritising the ecological values of the Hutt River valley. The Scoring Model developed in Appendix 5 of the Plan uses scoring criteria that allocates only 5% to “number of people directly affected” and “area directly effected” – and 60% to economic benefits. Furthermore, only 10% is allocated to environmental benefits.

This scoring criteria needs to be substantively reviewed.

From an economic point of view – it makes more sense to allocate value to people and ecological impact over the long-run (40-50 years) in order to exercise decisions, in the public interest, based on the most optimal economic value for the region. An economic decision based on short-term preferences, is a highly sub-optimal economic choice.

We believe that Environmental benefits need to have a higher score (and thus a priority) as the primary issue (flooding and Climate change) is caused by ecosystem failure. As the Hutt Valley is a natural flood plain, it makes intuitive sense to work along with this constraint using a more holistic, integrated design, led approach.

We believe that this is the root cause for why the current land-use recommendations are too minor to address the risks of residents over the 40 year planning horizon. A higher scoring for Environment, People and Areas affected will drive bigger, bolder economic choices.

A1. Development of a wetland area. Large part of the current low-lying, residential areas that are at significant risk – planned over a 40 year timeframe.

Benefits

- Long-Run robust ecological value and flood protection. Higher Ecological Integrity and increase of wildlife.
- Increase in hedonic value of surrounding properties

A2. Develop high value, integrated landscape designs (intellectual property) such as, the development of high value nature and recreational areas integrated with wetlands that attract economic growth integrated with ecological values.

The benefits of this policy are:

- High land valuations, accruing to increased rates and other taxable income to Government and to private wealth accounts.
- Reduced liability of flood damage via resilience

B. "Land Use for Business" – Develop economic prosperity through Business engagement

This is about local and regional business working closely with local authority planners to develop investment opportunity in business – at scale. [10]

To support this objective, we suggest that new monetary economic incentives be found.

B.1 Develop Tourism Markets for Hutt Valley

Intentionally develop Hutt Valley region as a high value tourism destination targeted to international visitor, youth and progressive, active adults. To achieve this, utilise market leading design practices and architecture graduate intern in design competitions to generate regional planning options for a better, more ecologically sound built environment for the Hutt River city.

The benefits of this policy are:

- The economic benefits can be measured in increased visitor numbers and therefore, increased visitor spend in New Zealand. (Economic, Public Benefit and Private Benefit)
- Increased intensive tourism in the Hutt Valley also takes away ecological pressure from tourism in New

Zealand's higher value ecological areas. (Environmental Benefit)

- Increased employment for NZ's high value design and engineering professional services (Economic, Labour Private Benefit)
- Increased Intellectual and Design Inventory (Economic)

The Hut Valley is located in close proximity to multiple natural reserves, recreational and sports facilities such as a golf course and a natural body of water.

The proximity to the Wellington international airport, rapid transport and modern amenities and possibly, high value office and entertainment provides an attractive proposition for tourists (demand side) and tourism operators (supply side).

In order to achieve this, land use changes will need to be prioritised towards development of more resilient, modern, designer offices and high-end residential facilities bordering recreational sites.

C. "Land Use for Community" - incentives for low-income households in the Hutt-Valley Region

C.1 Marketing of Natural Area Values of the Hutt Valley Region to its Communities

International research [1] substantiates the view that the most vulnerable segments of urban society tend to be the poorest, worst off economically. The learning costs towards adaptation are higher. Government costs associated with supporting low socio economic regions are higher than high socio economic regions and low socio economic regions generate tax revenue.

Research[7][8][9][13] also suggests that different cultures hold different value on natural resources.

Marketing and promotion activities therefore needs to be geared to engage more fully with the Hutt River – not just to "get through" a natural disaster. Marketing campaigns targeted based on market segment analysis. Marketing content needs to be audience focused, based on socio-economic status, cultural diversity and objectives for engaging with the Hutt River – recreation, conservation, restoration, volunteering and commer-

cialisation (tourism) opportunities. Digital, on line and mobile channels may be used to supplement this form of marketing.

Integrate Natural Area Value methodology into design of marketing campaigns.[8][9] Make flood management and disaster management integrated within this marketing – not a separate activity.

The benefits of this policy are:

- Increased participation in Hutt Valley’s natural areas. Increased ‘use value’ of Hutt Valley’s resources.
- Increased social cohesion and social fabric in the Hutt Valley over a 40 year timeframe. Natural Resources develop ‘common ground’ across multiple cultures.
- Increased ‘hedonic value’ of privately held property in the Hutt Valley region. Substantive research suggests and causal link between private land bordering high value natural resources.
- Increased learning opportunities for adaptation in flood management – especially within a community context.

This policy could deliver better adaptation outcomes in more cost-effective ways.

D. Buy-back scheme of the most flood-prone, low value privately held assets

This policy option is about purchasing of land that is exposed to recurrent flooding. Information on property titles [Appendix 2] should, as a matter of principle, reflect past flood events. From an economic valuation point of view, this will reduce market demand for those titles, reducing the cost-of purchasing the land. This would be in accordance with Government’s legal obligation of an transparent and fair market system. We suggest that the public sector should look at purchasing low-value housing stock to implement land-use changes at scale. Utilise market mechanisms that are available in a manner that generates net public benefits.

E. Adopt Open Information for Land use economic analysis

Land use information should, by default, become freely and publically available, without the use of specialised, proprietary computers or software.

For example: Publically available datasets about poten-

tial flood hazards are available from Wellington City Council via the Koordinates service, but this is missing data regarding the Hutt City and Flood Basin. [14]

Figure 1: GIS Datasets showing Flood Hazard Zones (red); Residential Zones (blue) and reserves [bright green]

The Benefits of this policy are:

- Reduced administrative costs for decision making. The internal ICT cost for an end user is NZD 15,920 per year. Open Data and open systems will provide a more cost effective way to provide key information to policy makers.
- Adaptive Management. Current indicators and their progress needs to be available in the public domain to enable adaptive management - which is necessary for ecological values. Adaptive management relies on contiguous information flow, information sharing and collaborative action between stakeholders – at scale.

Conclusion

We have proposed a range of policy options that will be more effective in addressing flood risk in the Hutt Valley region than the status quo options in the HRFPMP. We found several relevant research that reinforce the view that non-structural, more comprehensive approaches are necessary to address the significant flooding risk faced by the residents of Hutt Valley.

We went further than available literature by identifying a root cause for the failure to address long-run ecological value for this region – the HRFPMP weighted scoring method. We identified mitigating policies by attempting to integrate Regional Economic Development with Land Use policy which is designed to make flood control policies more affordable – whilst attracting more investment into the region.

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About the author

Nitish Verma brings a design-led approach to planning for results. His consulting and senior advisory career spans over 20 years in the NZ public sector. In this time he has helped government agencies adopt improved governance, risk management and legislative compliance processes; adopt ICT strategically and contribute to better public policy evaluation. He also serves as a business mentor in the community.

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